

Systematic Review Protocol

Urban planning and urban development to strengthen resilience to extreme climate events

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Abstract

Background Despite the growing body of literature on the key role of cities in mitigation and adaptation to climate change, there is less knowledge on how local approaches for resilience building in urban planning depend on global and national contexts. Given the growing emphasis on urban resilience in planning practice, a clearer understanding of how local planning challenges, strategies and tools are shaped by wider national and global frameworks is highly relevant. Current evidence, however, is dispersed across case studies and lacks systematic insights into the options and challenges of urban planning and urban development to strengthen climate resilience. To target this gap, this protocol outlines a systematic review designed to synthesize evidence on concepts and tools in urban planning for climate resilience and the influence of national contexts and conditions that cities are embedded in. The analysis of these linkages with quantitative data is novel.

Methods The review will be conducted in line with ROSES reporting standards and follow the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE) Guidelines. Searches will be conducted in Scopus and Web of Science using the topic search function in English. Critical appraisal on study-level will be carried out using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal checklist. For evidence-level appraisal we will use the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) Systematic Review Checklist. The dual blinded screening process will be based on pre-defined inclusion criteria and managed using the collaborative review platform Rayyan. Data extraction will be supported by the LLM-based software Elicit. We will apply a combination of qualitative interpretation and quantitative methods to synthesize the extracted data. This includes identifying patterns and contextual differences across urban planning and national settings, and examining these relationships using descriptive statistics and regression models.

Conclusions The results of the systematic review are expected to reveal that urban resilience building is shaped not only by local planning actions, but also by the broader national contexts and conditions in which cities are embedded in. The emerging insights may help clarify how these multi-level interactions influence urban planning and highlight areas where further research and policy development is needed.

Key words: urban planning, climate resilience, climate change adaptation, resilience strategies, literature review

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1. Introduction

The dual role of cities as both accelerators of climate change and highly exposed spaces to its consequences has been widely examined across disciplines, with extensive research analyzing responses to climate-related hazards. While a growing body of literature emphasizes the central role of cities in mitigation and adaptation to climate change (see e.g. Creutzig et al. 2022; Burley Farr et al. 2023; Solecki et al. 2024), considerably less is known about how local approaches to resilience building in urban planning are shaped by broader global and national contexts, such as specific regulation frameworks or funding structures. The envisaged review paper will systematically analyze existing literature on selected local approaches to strengthen resilience to climate extremes in urban planning. Next to the analysis of local approaches, we will assess the global and national contexts and the different typologies of selected cities for strengthening climate resilience. By assessing linkages between local action and national conditions as well as considerations on how factors such as urbanization, migration trends and extreme events influence urban planning strategies, we will provide a useful connection between the case-study based literature review and a quantitative assessment of typologies of cities in terms of human vulnerability and urbanization patterns. We anticipate that the novel analysis of these linkages with quantitative data will show that urban scale climate resilience building depends on local action, but also the national conditions that cities are embedded in.

Following RepOrting standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses in environmental research (ROSES) (Haddaway et al. 2018), this protocol for the proposed systematic review responds to the illustrated gaps by drafting a structured approach to identify, assess, and compare literature on local urban planning strategies for climate resilience building in relation to their respective city typologies as well as wider national and global contexts. By establishing a methodological framework for synthesizing evidence and capturing context-specific urban planning challenges, strategies, and tools for strengthening urban resilience to climate-related extreme events, this protocol sets the basis for generating a clearer understanding of how multi-level dynamics shape resilience pathways in cities worldwide. The planned evidence base is intended to support more informed and context-sensitive urban planning, to inform policy discussions on how national frameworks can better enable local action, and to identify priority areas for future research.

2. Objectives of the review

The review will systematically examine the existing body of research on urban planning to improve resilience to extreme climate events with a particular focus on planning-related challenges, strategies and tools. By means of a synthesis of current knowledge on local planning approaches, we aim to develop an integrated and current overview of how local planning approaches for resilience building to climate extremes depend on global and national contexts (e.g. regulations and funding). Thus, next to the analysis of local approaches and respective conditions, challenges and capacities, the review assesses the global and national contexts and the different starting points and typologies of selected cities for strengthening climate resilience. The global synthesis is based on a systematic review of relevant peer-reviewed literature with a clear focus on urban planning and climate-related hazards and risks. Using this information, we aim to explain how global and national contexts influence local conditions and the respective challenges and capacities for building resilience. We assess the links between local options and national conditions, taking into account how urbanization and migration trends, human vulnerability, and extreme events influence housing, land use and zoning. This establishes a useful link between case study-based literature research and a quantitative assessment of city typologies in terms of human vulnerability and urbanization patterns. Hence, a novel quantitative exploration of these interrelations is proposed. We will employ scientific databases (Web of Science and Scopus) to systematically review the literature on approaches applied in urban planning to enhance resilience to climate change and extreme events. The analysis of global and national contexts, covering

aspects such as human vulnerability, urban typologies, and urbanization dynamics, will draw on a range of different international datasets and index systems.

3. Methods

The review will follow the RepOrting Standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses (ROSES) review protocol (Haddaway et al. 2018). This recognized framework for evidence synthesis in environmental research will comprise the identification of relevant studies, screening according to predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the assessment of their eligibility. In addition, the review will include a critical appraisal of the study quality, followed by structured data extraction and analysis (Haddaway et al. 2018). The review process will be supported by the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE) Guidelines, which outline best practices for conducting systematic reviews and maps in environmental management and sustainability science (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018). The CEE framework provides detailed methodological guidance to enhance transparency, minimize bias, and ensure that the evidence synthesis is robust, reproducible, and policy-relevant. To facilitate key stages of the review, two digital AI-supported tools will be incorporated into the screening and data extraction stages in particular. The systematic review management platform Rayyan (<https://www.rayyan.ai/>), whose machine-learning-based auto-deduplication and similarity detection will enhance the efficiency and consistency of the screening process while ensuring adherence to systematic review methodology (Yu et al. 2022). Elicit (<https://elicit.com/>), a large-language-model-based research software will be used as a data extraction tool to pre-structure key variables during full-text data extraction. Both tools will be applied in an assistive manner to reduce workload and improve the organization and clarity of the evidence base, with all outputs subsequently reviewed and validated by the research team.

5. Stakeholder Involvement

ROSES reporting standards call for transparent presentation of the planned and actual role of stakeholders throughout the review process, beginning with the formulation of the overarching research questions for the systematic review. In this review, stakeholders are understood broadly in line with ROSES guidance, comprising the lead researcher, academic collaborators, and institutional actors involved in shaping the initial scope of the review. The overarching topic and framing emerged in consultation between the lead researcher, disciplinary experts, and associated partners engaged in the Environmental Research Letters (ERL) thematic context, who jointly contributed to refining the focus on urban planning approaches for resilience to extreme climate events.

During the operational phase of the review, the lead researcher provides overall conceptual direction, while the coordinating researcher is responsible for the organization and management of the systematic review e.g. search process, screening workflow, and adherence to methodological standards. In addition, further academic staff members and research assistants participate as screening and data-extraction contributors, conducting title/abstract and full-text screening in coordinated batches. Their involvement ensures diversified expert input, supports consistency checking, and contributes to methodological transparency. No external stakeholders beyond the academic team are involved in the execution of screening and data extraction. However, a group of international experts will be included for the analysis and synthesis part of the systematic review.

6. Search for Articles

Search Terms and search strings

The systematic search was designed to comprehensively capture peer-reviewed literature addressing the intersection of urban and spatial planning with climate-related extreme events and resilience strategies. The search strategy followed the ROSES guidelines (Haddaway et al. 2018) and methodological recommendations of the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018). The identification of search terms for the systematic review was carried out using a combination of different methods to be as exhaustive as possible while also limiting the number of irrelevant results (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 5.2.2). For determining the search terms and strings, the review of relevant articles for search terms was the decisive factor and was supplemented by discussions with members of the research team and searches in synonym databases.

Search sources and supplementary searches

With the Web of Science Core Collection (WoS) and Scopus, two major multidisciplinary databases are selected to ensure extensive coverage of international, peer-reviewed journals. Topic searches will be performed on both databases in the English language. No temporal restriction will be applied to ensure inclusion of earlier foundational studies. Boolean and proximity operators will be used to ensure conceptual breadth while maintaining relevance to the research topic. We have decided to focus exclusively on peer-reviewed academic literature for this systematic review. The final search string combined three thematic blocks: (1) urban and spatial planning terms, (2) climate-related extreme events, and (3) adaptation, strategies, and resilience. We have decided to exclude irrelevant subject areas (e.g. psychology, rural or ecological resilience, material sciences) at the search-level already, according to CEE guidelines section 5.2.3 (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 5.2.3). To ensure comprehensiveness and reduce the risk of omitting relevant studies, additional literature suggested by the supervisory team and ERL project partners will be considered as well, as this can allow the collection of especially relevant articles (Bayliss and Beyer 2015; Schindler et al. 2016). The inclusion of these expert-identified papers serves to validate the completeness of the systematic search rather than to expand it beyond its defined scope. In accordance with the CEE Guidelines (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 5.2.4), these additional sources will be subjected to the same screening process as database-derived records, and their origin will be documented to allow transparent evaluation of their potential influence. Grey literature will not be included, as the review aims to synthesize and evaluate the scientific, peer-reviewed evidence base on urban planning strategies for resilience to extreme climate events. This approach prioritizes methodological rigor and comparability across studies. The exclusion of grey literature is acknowledged as a limitation especially with regard to publication bias (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 3.2; Leimu and Koricheva 2005; Hopewell et al. 2007) but its impact is considered minimal given the research focus and the broad disciplinary coverage of indexed academic databases.

Search results

All retrieved records, including metadata (authors, year, title, abstract, journal, DOI, and keywords), will be exported from WoS and Scopus in RIS format and imported into the systematic review management platform Rayyan for title and abstract screening. The complete search history, database export files, and de-duplication logs will be archived and made available in the supplementary materials for transparency and reproducibility. Full texts will be obtained through Zotero using institutional subscriptions, open-access repositories, or direct author contact where necessary to ensure comprehensive coverage. If a potentially eligible study cannot be accessed in full text, we will request the document from the corresponding author, sending two inquiries spaced two weeks apart. Should we receive no response or be unable to obtain the full text through this way, the study will be excluded.

To ensure completeness and inclusion of the most recent research, an updated search will be conducted prior to data synthesis and manuscript submission. The update will replicate the original search strategy, databases, and filters, applying identical Boolean and proximity operators in both Web of Science and Scopus. The time window will extend from the last search date to the date of the update. Newly identified records will undergo the same de-duplication and dual-screening procedures described above. Any deviations from the original search protocol, including database functionality, indexing coverage, or syntax changes, will be transparently reported in the final review.

Estimation of the Comprehensiveness of the search

The search strategy is designed to capture a high conceptual spectrum of research at the intersection of urban planning and climate change adaptation or resilience in the context of climate-related extreme events. To this end, several exploratory searches will be used for iteratively testing and improving the search string. We estimate that this structure together with the expert-sourced articles ensures comprehensive coverage of both thematic and disciplinary perspectives relevant to the role of planning in building climate resilience. Through an initial pilot search and consultations with the project team, definitively eligible articles were identified as benchmark articles according to the eligibility criteria utilized, to estimate the comprehensiveness of the search string (Additional file 3). We used nine pre-identified key publications representing the core thematic scope of the review. The final search string was validated in Web of Science and Scopus to confirm retrieval of all benchmark articles. Where benchmark articles were not initially retrieved, missing keywords were added. This iterative validation ensured that the final search strategy comprehensively captured the core evidence base. The initial query was tested iteratively in Web of Science using pilot searches. All search parameters (database, date of search, fields searched, applied filters, and exact string syntax) are fully reported to ensure transparency and reproducibility (Additional file 2).

7. Article Screening

Screening process

To ensure transparency, reliability, and minimization of bias, article screening will follow a two-stage, fully dual and blinded process in accordance with ROSES standards (Haddaway et al. 2018), and the methodological guidance of the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, Section 6). Title and Abstract screening will be conducted simultaneously in Rayyan by six qualified and trained academic staff members working in three pairs, each responsible for one of three equally sized samples. Every record will thus be screened independently and blinded by two reviewers according to the pre-established inclusion and exclusion criteria. The division of the database into three samples and their distribution among the three screening teams is intended to ensure that each article is definitely screened dually, but that the workload is distributed evenly to ensure efficiency.

Prior to the main title/abstract screening, a pilot round of a small subset of 200 randomly selected records will be screened by two reviewers to calibrate inclusion criteria and ensure reliability. Agreement will be assessed by comparing the percentage of studies on which reviewers agreed or disagreed. As noted in the CEE guidelines, the interpretation of reviewer agreement is inherently subjective, and the goal of the pilot is not to achieve a particular threshold but to identify inconsistencies, clarify criteria, and ensure a shared understanding of the screening framework (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 6.3.4). To decide if to continue the screening process after the pilot or if to adapt screening criteria, we have agreed on targeting at least 80% inter-reviewer agreement. Any disagreements will be jointly reviewed, and minor adjustments or clarifications to the criteria will be made as needed. Once a satisfactory level of consistency has been reached, the review team will proceed to the full screening phase. Following calibration, each reviewer pair will independently screen all records within their assigned sample at both title/abstract and later, full-text level. All records will receive one of three

decisions: Include, Exclude, or Maybe. For each Exclude decision, one or more exclusion-reason labels will be applied to ensure transparency and traceability. After completion of the blinded phase, discrepancies between reviewers will be identified automatically in Rayyan and resolved through consensus discussion within each pair. If consensus cannot be reached, the coordinating researcher will adjudicate the final decision. All agreement statistics, percentages of disagreement, and resolution outcomes will be documented and reported to ensure methodological transparency. This comprehensive full dual-screening approach thus meets the requirements outlined in Section 6.3 of the CEE Guidelines, which recommend that “eligibility screening should be performed where possible by at least two people” and that independent screening is preferable (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 6.3). By implementing independent dual screening for 100% of the records, the review minimizes risks of individual bias and maximizes internal validity and reproducibility across all screening stages. All consensus meetings and adjudicated cases will be documented, including date, participants, and number of records discussed, to ensure full transparency of the decision-making process. This approach aligns with the CEE guidance, which emphasizes independent dual screening followed by consensus-based conflict resolution as best practice in systematic evidence synthesis (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 6.3.5).

Eligibility Criteria

In accordance with CEE and ROSES guidance, this review requires a clear and structured set of eligibility criteria to ensure a transparent and reproducible selection process. ROSES specifies that inclusion criteria should be organized according to the key elements of the review question, including subjects, interventions or exposures, comparators, outcomes, study designs, and any additional restrictions such as language or time period. ROSES standards also require that reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage be explicitly documented (ROSES 2017). The following section outlines these criteria as applied in this review.

Subjects

In the screening process, papers that focus explicitly on urban planning its challenges, instruments, strategies, and tools for increasing resilience to climate change and climate-related extreme events. The systematic review will therefore include studies situated in urban contexts with a clear focus on human systems within cities. Eligible studies must also refer to climate-related hazards or threats, such as extreme events (e.g. extreme heat, precipitation, flooding, drought). Rural, agricultural or natural-area settings will be excluded as well as papers on natural hazards that are not explicitly linked to climate change (e.g. earthquakes and tsunamis).

Intervention / Exposure

Studies must examine urban or spatial planning actions, instruments / tools, strategies, or governance processes that address climate-change related extreme events. Eligible planning interventions may include land-use planning, zoning, strategic urban adaptation plans, building regulations, nature-based planning instruments, or other institutionalized planning mechanisms. Informal or community-led adaptation efforts as well as technical concepts (e.g. GIS-based modeling) are eligible only if the link to planning systems is clearly articulated. Studies that merely “inform planning” through technical, ecological, purely geospatial, or socio-economic analyses, without analyzing the planning institutions, instruments, or decision-making involved, are excluded.

Comparator

No formal comparator is required for inclusion. However, studies may include implicit or explicit comparisons (e.g., between different cities, planning instruments, governance arrangements, or temporal phases). Such comparisons are permitted but not required for eligibility.

Outcomes

The review will include studies that examine how urban planning contributes to increasing resilience to climate change and climate-related extreme events, either through reducing vulnerability, enhancing adaptive capacity or adaptation actions, or improving institutional preparedness. Eligible outcomes include the development, implementation, or evaluation of planning measures; analyses of their impacts; and studies discussing barriers, challenges, or institutional constraints that limit effective climate-resilient planning. Studies that only describe climate impacts without addressing planning responses, or that focus solely on mitigation rather than adaptation or resilience, are excluded.

Study Design

Included studies may be empirical case studies (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods), comparative case studies, policy or planning evaluations, or conceptual/theoretical contributions that explicitly analyze planning instruments, governance mechanisms, or decision-making processes. Studies that present purely technical, ecological, engineering, or GIS-based approaches without examining planning strategies or governance are excluded. Likewise, studies providing only general approaches to support planning, without the role of urban planning, are not eligible.

Restrictions (Language, Hazard Type, language, date frame)

Only English-language publications will be included, as the review team does not have the capacity to reliably assess non-English full texts, and restricting the corpus ensures consistency and transparency in the application of eligibility criteria. The review focuses exclusively on climate-induced hazards and extreme events, including heatwaves, floods, storms and droughts. Studies addressing non-climatic hazards such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, or tsunamis are excluded because the drivers, governance mechanisms, and planning implications of these events differ fundamentally from climate-change-related extremes and would therefore fall outside the conceptual scope of the review. No publication date restrictions are applied, allowing the review to capture the full evolution of climate-resilient urban planning approaches over time. Studies from all world regions are eligible to ensure global coverage and to allow insights across diverse institutional, climatic, and socio-spatial contexts.

Reasons for Exclusion

A complete list of studies excluded at the full-text stage will be provided, including explicit reasons for exclusion in line with the criteria above.

Critical appraisal

Critical appraisal will be conducted at two levels: (1) study-level appraisal, where each included study is assessed; and (2) evidence-level appraisal, where the overall quality, consistency, and risk of bias across the evidence base are assessed to inform confidence in the final synthesis (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, Section 8).

Following CEE guidelines and ROSES standards, the methodological quality of each included study (study level appraisal) will be evaluated using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal checklist (Additional file 4). The appraisal will examine the appropriateness of the included study's aims, design, sampling and recruitment strategy, handling of confounding factors, data collection and analysis, and the overall credibility of the findings. Each JBI item will be rated as "yes," "no," "unclear," or "not applicable," and all results will be summarized in a quality assessment table. Consistency will be ensured through an initial calibration exercise in which two reviewers independently assess a small subset of studies to align interpretations of the JBI criteria. Any discrepancies will be discussed and resolved before full appraisal proceeds, and occasional cross-checks will be conducted to maintain coherence. To ensure consistency during the full critical appraisal process, one reviewer will appraise all included studies, while a second reviewer will independently assess a randomly selected sample of

at least ten percent. Inter-reviewer agreement will be evaluated and any discrepancies will be discussed until consensus is reached; if required, a third reviewer will be consulted. A concise summary of appraisal findings will be compiled to support transparent reporting (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, Section 8).

Following individual study appraisal, we will assess the evidence base as a whole by summarizing the distribution of study-level quality ratings, identifying recurring sources of bias, evaluating the consistency of findings across studies, and forming an overall judgement of confidence in the combined evidence (Additional file 5). To do so, we will be using the Critical Appraisal Skills Program (CASP) systematic review checklist (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme 2025). This narrative evidence-level appraisal follows CEE guidelines and will inform the interpretation of the synthesis (Collaboration for Environmental Evidence 2018, 8.3).

8. Data extraction and synthesis

Extraction strategy

Following the full-text screening stage, all included articles will be compiled into a reference library for data extraction. A structured extraction framework will be designed to collect key bibliographic details, study characteristics, and substantive findings from each publication as well as relevant criteria for the systematic review. The data-extraction framework will be informed by the pilot screening, conceptual literature on climate-resilient urban planning, refined through feedback sessions within the research team and external experts to ensure consistency and usability. For this purpose, we initially identified a set of effect modifiers that may contribute to heterogeneity in the included studies. These include the world region and respective national governance arrangements, city typologies, hazard type, challenges of urban planning to improve resilience and the resulting planning approach i.e. planned, autonomous or mixed (Maskell et al. 2025), as well as specific planning strategies developed and tools employed.

To support the data-extraction process, the review will employ Elicit (<https://elicit.com/>), a large-language-model-based research tool, as an assistive method for structuring and pre-populating the extraction fields. Elicit will be used to generate initial summaries and extract predefined variables (e.g. hazards, planning instruments, challenges, strategies, governance context), after which all outputs will be manually reviewed, verified, and corrected by the research team. The tool will not replace the research team's judgement; rather, it will reduce the time required for initial extraction processes and help ensure a consistent extraction of complex qualitative information across the full dataset. All LLM-assisted outputs will be transparently documented and incorporated only after validation to maintain methodological integrity and reproducibility. To ensure consistency and repeatability of the extraction process, a manual pilot reliability test will be conducted. A small, randomly selected sample of studies will be independently reviewed by two researchers using the draft extraction form. The extracted data will then be compared to identify discrepancies and assess the level of consistency across reviewers. Where differences are identified, the coding structure and definitions will be refined before proceeding with the full review to enhance clarity and repeatability. Where information in a study is incomplete or unclear, authors will be contacted to request clarification. If no response is obtained, the gap will be documented and the remaining data analyzed as available.

Data Synthesis and Presentation

Given the anticipated heterogeneity of study designs, contexts, and outcome measures in research on urban planning and extreme climate events, we will conduct a quantitative meta-analysis building on a thematic qualitative analysis as the primary analytic approach, structured around the variables defined in the data extraction framework and overlays with additional data such as income group of the respective countries, city size dependences and vulnerability levels. Following LLM-supported extraction, we will develop structured narrative evidence tables that summarize key study characteristics and enable comparison across planning instruments, governance contexts, adaptation measures, and

urban spatial settings. The lead author will oversee the analytical process in collaboration with the research team. Through iterative discussion, the team will refine thematic categories, interpret the extracted information, and develop integrative summaries that reflect common patterns, contextual differences, and limitations of the evidence base. To this end, we will develop a qualitative typology to characterize how planning tools, strategies, and challenges interact with city typologies national contexts in studies providing sufficient narrative detail. For the novel quantitative analysis, we will use a combination of basic descriptive statistics as well as regression analysis. First, we will produce basic counts and descriptive statistics for the main variables (challenges, strategies, tools, planning approaches, hazards, and national context indicators such as region, income level, or the presence of national adaptation frameworks). We will then cross-tabulate these codes to explore how challenges, strategies, and planning tools differ across national contexts and starting points. These comparisons will help identify patterns such as regional concentrations of specific challenges (e.g. capacity constraints, legal barriers), differences in tool portfolios (e.g. regulatory vs. nature-based), or shifts in planning strategies linked to governance structures. Building on the descriptive results, we intend to use regression models to assess the conditions under which particular strategies or tools are more likely to occur. Independent variables will include region, hazard type, planning approach (planned/autonomous/mixed), and available indicators of national planning systems, whereas dependent variables will capture the presence or diversity of challenges, planning tools and strategies. These models will allow us to examine whether, for example, more transformative planning strategies or more diverse tool combinations emerge under certain national governance conditions.

During data synthesis, we will assess potential publication bias by examining the distribution of included studies across regions, hazard types, and national planning contexts. Structural imbalances in the evidence base (e.g. overrepresentation of well-resourced planning systems or certain hazards will be documented and considered when interpreting patterns in challenges, strategies, and planning tools. These imbalances will be reported explicitly in the results and used to contextualize both the qualitative interpretation and the quantitative analyses.

9. Implications for research and policy

Despite considerable research on urban planning and its role to improve resilience to climate-related extreme events (e.g. Creutzig et al. 2022; Burley Farr et al. 2023; Solecki et al. 2024), critical knowledge gaps persist and there is still limited understanding of how local approaches to resilience building in urban planning are shaped by city typologies as well as national frameworks such as regulations and funding structures. Likewise, research remains scarce on the barriers and challenges that cities face specific to their national and regional contexts, and on the planning strategies and instruments they employ to strengthen resilience in response. We expect that the findings from this systematic review will provide notable insights and a systematic understanding of the different starting points of cities and city dwellers to build climate resilience with respect to the specific contexts of different world regions. Furthermore, we anticipate that the findings will show that urban scale planning approaches to strengthen resilience depend not only on local action but also on the national conditions that cities are embedded in. As the analysis of these linkages with quantitative data is novel, we expect that the findings from this systematic review could inform both research and policy by demonstrating how local resilience efforts in urban planning are shaped by broader national regulatory, financial, and socio-economic contexts. The review may thus highlight effective planning tools, common barriers, and promising governance arrangements, offering guidance for policymakers to better align local resilience mandates with supportive national frameworks. At the same time, the results can point to key research gaps, including the need for comparative studies across regions, improved analytical frameworks for multi-level adaptation processes, and deeper investigation of planning strategies, instruments and tools. Together, these insights can support more coherent policy design and more context-sensitive research on urban climate resilience.

10. Conclusions

The systematic literature review aims to advance current understanding of how urban resilience building through urban planning emerges from the interaction between local planning practices and the broader national and global conditions in which cities operate. By combining a systematic assessment of local planning approaches to strengthen resilience with an analysis of context-specific vulnerability patterns, governance frameworks, and urbanization trends, we expect the study will clarify why cities in distinct world regions differ markedly in their capacities to prepare for climate extremes. The resulting evidence base is expected to support more informed and context-sensitive urban planning, highlight where national policies can better enable local approaches, and identify promising directions for future research on multi-level climate resilience. Ultimately, the review seeks to contribute to a more nuanced and globally relevant perspective on how cities and their residents can strengthen resilience under increasingly complex climatic and socio-economic pressures.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no financial or non-financial conflict of interests.

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